

Labeo molybdinus Leaden labeo

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Phylum: Chordata

Estimated genome size: 1 560 million DNA base pairs (1.56 Gigabases)
Organism size: 38 cm (max length)

Distribution:

The Leaden labeo is found across Southern Africa, inhabiting the Limpopo, Incomati, Usutu, Tugela, and Zambezi River systems.

Importance:

The Leaden Labeo is a freshwater fish endemic to Southern Africa. To fully understand its phylogenetic relationships and the evolutionary history and diversification of the *Labeo* genus in Africa, comprehensive genomic data are crucial. Currently listed as Least Concern on the IUCN Red List, the Leaden Labeo is experiencing population declines due to a range of documented threats. It is occasionally targeted in recreational angling and plays a significant role in subsistence fisheries.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 49.99 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 5.41 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics: Genome length: 1.02 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 99.6%
[Single: 96.1%, Duplicated: 3.5%]

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